

THE ROLE OF VOIDS IN REDUCING THE INTERLAMINAR SHEAR STRENGTH IN RTM LAMINATES

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SUMMARY: Void shape, size and content were investigated in laminates containing two different carbon reinforcements, manufactured by resin transfer moulding (RTM). The effect of voids in each laminate system on the interlaminar shear strength was determined and a difference in the void-strength relationship between the two laminates was observed. The difference was correlated to the variation in void morphology, arising from the different pore-space geometries of the reinforcements. The fracture mechanism of the short beam shear test and the effect of voids on crack failure behaviour during this test were investigated. Cracks were observed to initiate from medium to large sized voids with sharp corners, but not from small spherical voids. Voids were also observed to affect the crack propagation path, with cracks terminating at voids.

KEYWORDS: voids, resin transfer moulding, fracture mechanisms, interlaminar shear strength

INTRODUCTION

The basic aim of the resin injection stage in resin transfer molding (RTM) is to completely fill a reinforcement preform with resin without the formation of defects. Defects can cause a reduction in the mechanical properties of polymer composites [1]. Defects common to the RTM laminate are commonly referred to as dry spots, voids or porosity [2]. A dry spot is defined as a region of preform that has not been filled by resin while porosity is primarily caused by the mechanical entrapment of air or volatiles [3-5]. This entrapment arises from the combination of an irregular resin flow front and obstructions within the reinforcement, such as crimps and stitches [5]. Leaks are a problem in vacuum-assisted RTM, allowing air to displace resin from the impregnated preform and thus creating voids.

Lundstrum *et.al.* have shown that voids formed within fibre tows have the shape of cylindrical tubes, while voids formed between tows resemble spherical bubbles [6]. The size and geometry of the free space located between fibre tows is a function of the fabric design and level of compaction within the preform. This free space influences the morphology of bubbles, which are not always spherical in shape. Therefore, RTM laminates with different reinforcements will have different void shapes and sizes. The mechanisms of void formation, the level of bubble transport during mould filling, and void stability during cure will

determine the distribution and content of voids within the laminate. Parameters such as injection pressure, vacuum assistance, resin viscosity and wet-out all influence void formation, stability and transport during the RTM process [3,6].

The effect of voids on the mechanical properties of polymer composites has been reported in a number of papers. Many researchers use the interlaminar shear strength test (ILSS) to investigate the effect of voids on the strength of a laminate. A comparison of published results shows a significant variation in the decrease in strength caused by void content. Ghiorse determined that the differences can be related to the accuracy of the void content measurement technique used [7]. Oliver *et.al.* showed how void size differences within prepreg laminates of identical void content can cause a difference in the extent of strength reduction [8] while Hancox suggested that void locations, shapes and sizes may influence the values of measured strengths [9].

While previous research studies have identified the general morphology of voids in RTM laminates, and other research studies have suggested that void morphology influences the level of strength reduction, there is a lack of research combining these two areas. The objectives of this study were to determine how different fabric types influence the size, shape and distribution of voids within carbon/epoxy RTM laminates, and how the nature of voids formed within the laminate affect the interlaminar shear strength. It is considered important to combine property data on void-strength effects with detailed investigations into the void location, shape and size for specific laminate systems to help determine the mechanism by which voids reduce the ILSS. Post-test optical image analysis studies of defective and non-defective RTM laminate coupons were also carried out to determine the types of failure cracks common to the ILSS test, and how such cracks interact with voids.

EXPERIMENTAL

Specimen Manufacture

Carbon/Epoxy Laminates

Two laminate systems were selected to determine the effect of void shape, size and location on the interlaminar shear strength. The difference between the laminates was the type of weave for the carbon reinforcement selected. Two 3K AS4 carbon fibre fabrics, supplied by Ciba Composites, a plain weave of 200 g/m² and a 5-harness satin weave of 285 g/m² were used. Figure 1 shows the weave geometry of each fabric type. The epoxy was a three part system (Araldite F), containing LY 556 resin, HY 918 hardener and DY 052 catalyst. The mix ratio was 100:90:1 (resin:hardner:catalyst). The fibre volume fraction was calculated as 57% for both laminates.

Laminate Manufacture

The laminates were manufactured by RTM using a pressure pot as the injection source. An aluminium mould base with cavity dimensions of 480 mm x 13 mm x 3.2 mm was used, with a toughened glass plate as the mould top. Resin was injected at one end of the mould, and air was removed from the opposite end. A partial vacuum (-80 kPa) was applied to the mould outlet during injection. The injection pressure was 200 kPa, and the mould temperature was 20°C. After injection the laminates were cured at 80°C for one hour.

Fig. 1: Schematic diagram identifying reinforcement geometry for a plain weave and 5-harness carbon fabric

Defect (Void) Formation

Defective laminates were produced with varying levels of porosity content. This was achieved by intentionally producing a dry spot within the panel. The level of porosity around the perimeter of a dry spot varied from 0 to 20% void volume fraction (V_v). During the initial stages of injection the resin was allowed to “racetrack” around the perimeter of the preform. The resin reached the outlet before the preform was completely filled, resulting in the formation of an unfilled region. The inlet end of the panel was already completely filled out when the dry spot was originally formed. The porosity content within the inlet region of the panel was between 0 and 2% V_v . The flow front through the preform in this region of the panel was relatively smooth, with the resin flow front between the tows slightly ahead of the flow front within the tows. Any bubbles formed were flushed towards the flow front edge near the dry spot perimeter. When the dry spot was trapped, the flow front around it became slow and irregular, with resin leading within the tows. This led to the entrapment of voids between the tows around the perimeter of the dry spot. During the early stages of cure, the resin continued to move into the dry spot region within the tows, while porosity remained between the tows.

Void Content Determination

The void content, shape, size and location within a section of the laminate was determined by Optical Image Analysis. The image analysis system included a Reichart optical microscope, a Videk camera, a Videk Megaplus frame grabber, and a Macintosh computer with the image analysis software Image 1.58. Non-destructive Ultrasonic C-scan inspection was also used to determine the void content throughout a laminate panel. The equipment used was an Infometrics “Test Pro” system and a Meccasonic laboratory scanning tank. The Test Pro is a PC based ultrasonic testing instrument incorporating scanning frame control. Ultrasonic

signals were provided by a Panametrics receiver (model 5052PR), driving a 15MHz focused probe. The total system gain was 26 dB. The scanning grid was 1mm x 1mm.

In selecting an ILSS test coupon, a laminate section adjacent to it in the panel was used to estimate the void content of the mechanical test specimen. This was done by locating two adjacent samples which contained the same level of surface porosity and the same level of dB loss. The level of surface porosity was determined by OIA. The level of dB loss was determined by C-scan analysis. One of the adjacent sections, which had the same dimensions as the potential test coupon, was then cross-sectioned into three segments. The samples were mounted in polyester resin, and finely polished by an automatic Prepamatic polishing machine. The porosity content was determined at X32 magnification, with 6 random areas chosen from each of the three segments. The average of 18 measurements was calculated and taken to be the volumetric porosity content of the coupon.

Interlaminar Shear Strength Testing

The interlaminar shear strength test was conducted according to the short beam shear test method ASTM D2344. Fifty samples for each laminate system were selected from defective laminates, which contained varying porosity contents, to determine the effect of void content, size, shape and location on the interlaminar shear strength. The ILSS coupons were prepared by cutting with a diamond saw, and the sides polished with 400 wet and dry paper to remove any flaws caused by cutting. The tests were performed using an INSTRON 4505 mechanical testing machine. A 100 kN load cell was used, with the crosshead speed set at 1.3 mm/min. The dimensions of the specimens were 19.2 mm x 6.4 mm x 3.2 mm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Void Characterisation for Carbon/Epoxy Laminates

Void Shape

A comparison of the voids present in the two carbon fabric composites was made for the laminates containing less than 10% V_v porosity. In the plain weave laminate, the most common void shape observed between the tows was an elliptical bubble, as shown in Fig. 2. At the ply interface, the bubbles were observed to be linked, forming a much larger void, but this void tended to retain a symmetrical shape, with the corners avoiding a low radii of curvature. For the 5-harness weave laminate, the shape of voids located between tows ranged from elliptical to the more common asymmetric shaped void, as shown in Fig. 3. The radii of curvature of the asymmetric voids varied between 5 and 20 μm for the 5-harness fabric, compared with 35 to 110 μm for the elliptical bubbles observed in the plain weave fabric, as shown in Fig. 4. The higher irregularity in void shape for the 5-harness fabric compared to the plain weave fabric can be explained in terms of the fabric design.

The 5-harness fabric is a much tighter knit compared with the plain weave fabric, as shown in Fig. 1. The distance between adjacent fibre tows for the plain weave fabric is typically 0.5 mm, compared with 0.1 mm for the 5-harness fabric. The available space at a fibre tow intersection is larger than that between adjacent tows for both fabrics. A plain weave fabric contains five times more fibre tow intersections per ply than a 5-harness fabric. A plain weave fabric, therefore, would be expected to accommodate larger bubbles with more energetically

favourable shapes at fibre tow intersections. This was confirmed by through-thickness OIA of void-containing laminates.

Fig. 2: Micrograph showing void morphology in the plain weave carbon laminate

Fig. 3: Micrograph showing void morphology in the 5-harness carbon laminate

Fig. 4: Distribution of radii of curvature of voids located in the plain weave and 5-harness laminates

Void Size and Distribution

The size of each void was characterised by its cross-sectional area, for a known void content. This showed that the 5-harness composite contained a higher quantity and distribution of small voids (usually asymmetric in shape), than the plain weave laminate, which contained a higher level of medium to large voids, but a relatively low quantity of small voids.

The majority of the large voids within the plain weave laminate did not contain sharp corners. This contrasted with the 5-harness laminate where, within the 5 to 8.6% V_v range, the majority of the available pockets between tows were occupied by a sharp-cornered void.

For the plain weave fabric the size of voids which incorporated no more than two adjacent fibre tow intersections varied from 50 μm to 1.2 mm in length, and 20 to 500 μm in height. For the 5-harness fabric, the size of an equivalently positioned void ranged from 50 μm to 3 mm in length, and 20 to 350 μm in height. With a loose knit design, such as the plain weave fabric, voids had greater through-thickness linkage, while for the 5-harness fabric voids had greater in-plane linkage.

Effect of Porosity on ILSS for Carbon/Epoxy Laminates

Level of ILSS Reduction

Fig. 5 compares the effect of porosity on the interlaminar shear strength for the two different laminate systems. For the 5-harness fabric laminate the trend showed a 7% reduction in ILSS per 1% increase in porosity up to 10% V_v . The plain weave fabric laminate showed a 4% reduction in ILSS per 1% increase in porosity over this range.

Fig. 5: Effect of porosity on ILSS for Carbon (5H,3K)/Araldite-F RTM laminate and for Carbon (plain weave, 3K)/Araldite-F RTM laminate

The failure of the short beam shear coupons tested in this study were mainly dependent on the formation of a series of inter- and intra-laminar cracks, rather than by one single crack. The effect of voids on reducing the strength of the laminate can be observed by its influence on crack failure. Intralaminar cracks were observed to initiate at voids, as seen in Fig. 6 [11]. These intralaminar cracks propagated to the ply interface, and were transformed into interlaminar cracks.

Fig. 6: Micrograph of failed ILSS coupon showing crack failure at voids.

The difference in the effect of porosity on the ILSS for the plain weave and 5-harness laminates, seen in Fig. 5, can be attributed to the void morphology, size, and distribution [8,9]. Firstly, the 5-harness fabric contains a higher level of asymmetric voids with corners of lower radii compared with the more symmetrically shaped elliptical voids within the plain weave composite. Voids of lower radii of curvature lead to higher stress concentrations [10]. Therefore, a crack is more likely to initiate at a sharp void than a smooth-cornered void. In addition, the voids in the 5-harness laminate were of greater length, which results in a higher stress intensification [11]. Furthermore, cracks are likely to be initiated in a 5-harness laminate at a lower applied stress due to the higher population and distribution of voids throughout the laminate.

Post-mortem Study of ILSS Coupons for Carbon/Epoxy Void-Free Laminates

Microcracks

Further analysis of ILSS carbon/epoxy composite beams showed the presence of resin microcracks at the initiation point of intralaminar and interlaminar cracks within the central region of the beam. It appeared that crack initiation occurred at the fibre/matrix interface, with the microcracks being oriented at 45° to the longitudinal fibres, and ultimately coalescing into larger intralaminar and delamination cracks. The form of these cracks were similar to those referred to as 'shear hackles' which are a fracture characteristic observed in mode II studies. They have been identified as a series of parallel platelets of fractured resin formed perpendicular to the maximum resolved tensile stress[12].

CONCLUSIONS

The main findings of this study were:

- The 5-harness laminates contained a greater number of small asymmetric voids than the plain weave laminates, which contained larger, spherical voids. This is attributed to the different reinforcement geometry and resulting 'free' space within the fabric .
- The reduction in ILSS for plain weave laminates was less than that of 5-harness laminates with comparable void content. This resulted from the greater numbers of cracks formed in the 5-harness laminates due to the higher population of sharp-cornered voids.
- Both intra and inter-laminar cracks formed during ILSS testing and resin microcracks were also observed. Voids acted to initiate cracks.

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